

A Study to Assess the Effectiveness of Pranayama on Stress Among Antenatal Mothers Attending Antenatal Clinic in People's Hospital of Bhopal (M.P.)

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ABSTRACT

Pranayama is the best way to control energy through breathing. It works instantly & relieves stress and boosts energy. Regular pranayama practice is refreshing and balances emotions. Pranayama is scientifically proved tool to reduce the anxiety level and negative emotions.

The aim of the study was to assess the effectiveness of the Pranayama on reducing Stress among antenatal mothers. A total 40 antenatal mothers were studied. The duration of the study was 4 weeks, and change outcomes were measured at the beginning & at the end of the study with help of questionnaire.

Pre-test mean and SD were 62.45 & 11.46 respectively where as post test mean and SD were 32.90 & 7.90, with Chi-value 65.1538 and tabulated value at 0.0001. These reading indicated the effectiveness of Pranayama on Stress among antenatal mothers.

KEY WORDS: Study, effectiveness, pranayama, stress, antenatal mothers, antenatal clinic, hospital

INTRODUCTION:

Indian Statistical Report (2017) stated that (recent Nielsen surveys on stress in 6500 women), that the 87% of Indian women claim feeling stressed most of the time, with an additional 82% asserting that they had insufficient time to relax. The biggest stress is felt among women of 25-55 years of age, who are trying to balance demanding careers with obligation at home. The data indicate the percentage of women claiming to be stressed most of the time. India (87%), Mexico (74%), Russia (69%), Brazil (67%), Spain (66%), France (65%), South Africa (64%), Italy (64), Nigeria (58%), Turkey (56%). According to the data Indian tops the list.^[1]

Stress is the feeling of emotional or physical tension. Stress is the consequence of failure of a human to respond appropriately to emotional or

physical threats.

It is a major health hazard of the modern world affecting all people irrespective of age, gender, education, occupation, domiciliary status, finance, religion, race, ethnicity, and nationality.^[2]

The antenatal period of the baby is a crucial time for neurodevelopment of the body and is thus a period of vulnerability during which a range of symptoms have been found to exert long-term changes on brain development and behavior with implications for physical and psychiatric health.^[3]

OBJECTIVES:

- To assess the pre-existing level of stress among antenatal mothers attending antenatal clinic in selected hospital.
- To find out the effectiveness of pranayama techniques on level of stress among antenatal mothers attending antenatal clinic in selected hospital.
- To assess the post level of stress among antenatal mothers attending antenatal clinic with socio-demographic variables in selected hospital.
- To find out the association between post-test level of stress among antenatal mothers attending

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Table 1: Analysis of Difference Between Pre-Test and Post-Test

	MEAN	SD	Chi-value	df	t - value	Significant
Pre test	62.45	11.46	65.1538	78	4.10	Significant at p value
Post test	32.90	7.90				

antenatal clinic in selected hospital.

- To compare the pre and post level of stress after Pranayama techniques among antenatal mothers attending antenatal clinic in selected hospital.

HYPOTHESIS:

H₀: There will be no significant difference between pre-test and post-test stress level among antenatal mothers attending antenatal clinic in selected hospital.

H₁: There will be significant association between demographic variable and post-test stress level among antenatal mothers attending antenatal clinic in selected hospital.

H₂: There will be significant difference between pre-test and post-test stress level among antenatal mothers attending antenatal clinic in selected hospital.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

In this study an experimental research design and quantitative evaluative approach is used. The sample consisted of 40 antenatal mothers, by using purposive sampling technique. The conceptual framework is used for the study was modified King's attainment theory of goal attainment. Tool used for data collection was self- structure questionnaires, by the investigator related to effects of Pranayama on reducing Stress among antenatal mothers attending antenatal clinic in selected hospital.

RESULTS:

- Majority of samples i.e. (37.5 %) were in between 25-30 years of age, (25%) were in between 31-35 years of age (20%) were in between 36-40 years of age and (17.5%) were in between 41-45 years of age of Pranayama on stress among antenatal mothers attending antenatal clinic in selected hospital.
- Majority of samples i.e. 15(37.5%) were from business and others, 8(20%) were private job and 2(5%) were government job of Pranayama on stress among antenatal mothers attending antenatal clinic in selected hospital.
- Majority of samples i.e. 20(50%) were from field worker, 10 (25%) were from housewife, 5 (12.5%) were from office worker and 5

Figure 1: Difference between Pre-test & post-test

(12.5%) were from others of Pranayama on stress among antenatal mothers attending antenatal clinic in selected hospital.

- Majority of samples i.e. 20 (50%) were having from husband bad habit and 20(50%) were not having from husband bad habit of Pranayama on stress among antenatal mothers attending antenatal clinic in selected hospital.

To provide pranayama for 30 min per day for 30 days among antenatal mothers attending antenatal clinic in selected hospital.

Pranayama was demonstrated to the antenatal mothers and was supervised thereafter, antenatal mothers repeated pranayama everyday for 30 min for 30 days.

The analysis of post-test was significant decrease in level of stress . Post-test mean and SD were 32.90 & 7.90, t-test value 13.4308, df 78, tabulated value 4.10.

The analysis pre-test and post-test significant, chi-value 65.1538 and significant of p value 0.0001.

Table 2 describe that pre-test mean and SD were 62.45 & 11.46 respectively where as post test mean and SD were 32.90 & 7.90, with chi-value 65.1538 and tabulated value at 0.0001. these reading indicate the effectiveness of Pranayama on stress among antenatal mothers.

Table 2: Describe that pre-test mean and SD.

	Mean	SD	Mean Difference	Chi value with p value
Pre- test	62.45	11.46	29.55	65.1538
Post-test	32.90	7.90		

CONCLUSION:

The study was done to evaluate the effectiveness of Pranayama on stress among antenatal mothers attending antenatal clinic in People's Hospital, Bhopal. Following conclusion are drawn from the present study findings are :-

- Stress among antenatal mothers decreases after performing Pranayama.
- Pre-test mean and SD were 62.45 & 11.46 respectively whereas post-test mean & SD were 32.90 and 7.90 respectively with t-test value 13.4308, df 78, tabulated value 4.10. These reading indicate that Pranayama is quite affective to deduce stress among antenatal mothers attending antenatal clinic in selected hospital.

NURSING EDUCATION:

Nursing must be encouraged to utilize their knowledge on promotive measure by health education and demonstration in Hospital.

NURSING ADMINISTRATION:

Administrators should take initiative action to update the knowledge of nursing personnel regarding Pranayama to improvement of health and reducing the stress among antenatal mothers by in service education. Nurse administrators can conduct workshop and seminar on Pranayama for reducing stress to all level of nursing personnel in the Hospital.

NURSING RESEARCH:

Evidence based practice helps the nurses to enrich them in knowledge and practice. Nursing researcher should be directed to toward exploring the advantages of Pranayama can be improved. The present study revealed that there the practice of Pranayama should be encouraged in order to decrease the stress among antenatal mothers. The findings of the

present study shall provide a baseline data for research studies to be conducted in future.

LIMITATIONS:

This study will be limited to-

- 40 antenatal mothers attending antenatal clinic in People's hospital, Bhopal.
- Antenatal mothers who can understand English or Hindi.
- Antenatal mothers who are willing to participation in the study.
- To the experience level of the researcher.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

The following studies can be undertaken to strengthen Pranayama as a good remedy for Decrease the stress among antenatal mothers

This study can conduct with larger number of samples.

A study can be conducted with more than 30 days intervention.

REFERENCES:

1. Mudakavi I. Stress & coping strategies among homemakers. Intern J Practical Nur. 2017;5.
2. Basheer SP. A Concise Textbook of Advanced Nursing Practice. 1st Edn. Bangalore: Emmess Medical Publishers. 2012.
3. Sowmiya V. Effectiveness of pranayams on stress and coping among housewives in selected community, salem (Tamilnadu). 2012.
4. Polit DF. Nursing Research Principles and Methods. Philadelphia: Lippincott. 1999.
5. Kaur A. Textbook of psychology”. 1st edition. New Delhi: Peevee Publications. 2013.
6. Basavanthappa BT. Nursing research. 3rd Edn. New Delhi: reprint Jaypee brothers Publications. 2007.
7. Lalitha K. Mental Health and Psychiatric Nursing an Indian Perspectives. Bangalore: V.M.G Book house publication. 2010.
8. Kapoor B. Textbook of Psychiatric Nursing. 2nd Edn. New Delhi: Kumar publishing house. 2010.
9. Mahajan BK. “Methods of Biostatistics. 6th Edn. New Delhi: Mosby Company. 2007.

Cite this article as: Priya A, Bhargav N, Gupta RR: A Study to Assess the Effectiveness of Pranayama on Stress Among Antenatal Mothers Attending Antenatal Clinic in People's Hospital of Bhopal (M.P.). PJSR. 2022;15(2):27-29. Source of Support : Nil, Conflict of Interest: None declared.